

Socio-technical factors generating social debt

Table 3: Coordination factor.

Id	Cause and primary studies
COF1	Inadequate management of inter-task dependencies [PS1–PS8, PS21, PS27–PS32].
COF2	Lack of clear distribution of responsibilities, poorly defined roles, and tasks assigned to a limited number of team members without redundancy [PS1–PS9, PS27–PS32].
COF3	Excessive pressure creating bottlenecks [PS1–PS8, PS27–PS45].
COF4	Lack of coordination between teams due to unshared technical decisions [PS1–PS8, PS27–PS45].
COF5	Coordination difficulties in multi-team environments, often caused by poor communication [PS1–PS8, PS21, PS27–PS45].
COF6	Lack of adequate iterative planning [PS3, PS4, PS21].
COF7	Lack of coordination between processes and roles, resulting in uncontrolled dependencies [PS1–PS8, PS21, PS23, PS27–PS45].
COF8	Informal coordination among architects, developers, and clients [PS1–PS8, PS21, PS27–PS45].
COF9	Challenges caused by frequent reorganizations or weak agile coordination structures [PS1–PS10, PS21, PS22, PS26–PS45].
COF10	Bottlenecks caused by the concentration of responsibilities in individual leaders [PS1–PS9, PS27–PS45].
COF11	Unreported changes leading to inconsistencies [PS1–PS8, PS23, PS27–PS45].
COF12	Poor coordination due to structural differences, geographical distance, and time zone misalignment [PS1–PS8, PS24, PS27–PS45].
COF13	Lack of structured coordination due to implicit governance, with no clear rules or established processes [PS1–PS9, PS27–PS45].
COF14	Excessive procedural burden and lack of process clarity [PS1–PS8, PS10, PS21, PS27–PS45].
COF15	Low team cohesion and misalignment of roles [PS1–PS8, PS27–PS45].
COF16	Lack of gender diversity associated with poor coordination dynamics [PS1–PS8, PS27–PS43].
COF17	Parallel software development without communication among developers [PS1–PS8, PS23, PS27–PS43].
COF18	Lack of mechanisms for sharing architectural responsibilities across roles [PS1–PS9, PS27–PS43].
COF19	Inconsistent assignment of teams and roles, resulting from poorly defined organizational structures [PS1–PS9, PS27–PS43].
COF20	Low socio-technical congruence [PS1–PS8, PS23, PS27–PS45].
COF21	Negative emotional states or prolonged stress [PS1–PS8, PS25, PS27–PS43].
COF22	Filtered interactions and communication delays due to fear of sharing critical information [PS1–PS8, PS21, PS27–PS43].
COF23	Changes in work routines and increased isolation among team members [PS1–PS9, PS27–PS43].

Acronyms used: Coordination factor (COF).